

CoARA Boost Cascade Funding – Call 1

Progress Report

Project	
Project number	24-CoARA-072
Name of the project	Evaluating the Impact of Reformed Research Assessment and the use of Narrative CV's in Academic Career Promotion at Swansea University.
Type of project	<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional change <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional pilot
Reporting period	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> M0 - M6 <input type="checkbox"/> M7 - M12
Reporting deadline	June 25 th , 2025
Date of last update of the report	

Organisation	
Organisation name Please fill-in information in red for Teaming Project's coordinator	Contact Name, mail address

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1. Purpose of the CoARA Cascade Funding Progress Report

The CoARA Cascade Funding Progress Report serves as a tool for supporting beneficiaries of the program in sharing progress with the CoARA Secretariat, and, upon request, the European Commission. It provides a framework to track progress, monitor activities, and bring transparency in how resources are used during the reporting period.

Additionally, the template facilitates continual reflection and documentation of the projects, allowing for a comprehensive overview of their activities, achievements.

For Teaming projects, please note that one Progress Report is expected per project.

Please note that this monitoring report template covers the technical aspect of the progress reporting and that the Excel table “Project Budget template” covers the financial part. Please fill in the Excel table according to your type of project:

- Annex 4 - for mono-beneficiary (i.e., Institutional Pilot Calls and Institutional Change Calls):

<https://coara.eu/app/uploads/2025/02/Projects-budget-template-unique-partner-1.xlsx>

OR

- Annex 5 - for partnering projects (i.e., Teaming Calls - each partner must complete one sheet in the document):

<https://coara.eu/app/uploads/2025/02/Projects-budget-template-partnering-projects-1.xlsx>

Both documents are mandatory and expected to be submitted to complete the reporting milestones in M06 and M12.

Please send back your report, your use of resources (Excel budget table) and your annexes (if applicable) by June 25th, 2025, to secretariat@coara.eu

2. Monitoring system

To ensure easy monitoring of the progress made in the funded projects, the monitoring system consists of the following parts:

- Progress measurement base (section 2.1.)
- Progress reporting (section 2.2.)
- Dissemination activities (section 2.3)
- Next Steps (section 2.4)
- Budget Monitoring (section 2.5)

2.1. Progress measurement base: Work plan

Please provide a hyperlink or summary of your work plan for the **M0 - M6 period** in the box below.

Evaluating the Impact of Reformed Research Assessment and the use of Narrative CV's in Academic Career Promotion at Swansea University.

Tasks 1-3 are covered within the M0-M6 period within the Work Plan submitted:

Task 1: Invitations to academic staff to apply for promotion (September 2024- December 2024) HR driven process outside of the remit of this project but planned activity will include support for staff applying for promotions in the guise of training, webinars, workshops and mentoring. These activities will inform the review and evaluation.

Task 2: Undertake Process evaluation of resources and support provided to applicants, panels and reviewers (December 2024 - June 2025). The markers of success will be having a Research analyst in post by December 2024, self-Evaluation framework adapted for use by December/January when the anonymised data capture will begin from both applicants and reviewers.

Task 3: Narrative CV impact assessment #1: (January - July 2025) Data analysis evaluating how the narrative CV is being used by reviewers and panels, and how this is changing the way research is assessed and recognised.

2.2. Progress reporting

This section aims to facilitate reporting of progress for all projects, and coordination of partners for Teaming projects.

2.2.1. Reporting process

The table and text boxes below provide a simplified method to report on projects' progress quantitatively and qualitatively. Please add as many rows as required.

Outputs/ Deliverables/ Activity	Brief description	Its relevance to ARRA commitments Which commitment is addressed and how?	Hyperlink to final version if available	Timeframe MM/YY	Funding acknowledgement (if available)
Promotion applications using the reformed Academic Career Pathways (ACPs)	Staff at Swansea University (SU) invited to apply for promotions using the reformed ACPs that have incorporated a narrative style CV to assess research and innovation capacity	1-6, The reformed criteria in the ACPs (which were developed through consultation across SU and the research and Innovation (R&I) community) aim to recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research. Reducing the use of metrics and other quantitative indicators of	Academic Career Pathways - Swansea University	09/24-03/25	n/a The ACP reform started in 2022 and is a university wide process beyond the scope of the current project

		<p>success, basing research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central</p>			
<p>Swansea University CoARA boost information sheet and Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs)</p>	<p>We have created an information sheet based on initial feedback from the research community at SU, incorporating the FAQs from academics</p>	<p>6 & 7 The info and FAQ sheet can be used as a tool to support research assessment reform and aims to raise awareness and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use</p>	n/a	07/25	n/a (plan to publish)
<p>Information Webinar on ACPs and promotion</p>	<p>The PVC for R&I invited all academic staff to an informational webinar and Q&A</p>	<p>5-7: The webinar provided training and guidance to staff, communicated</p>	n/a	01/25	n/a

	discussing the reformed research assessment	the tools and resources available to staff to support them with their applications, and communicated the commitment of SU to research assessment reform			
Workshop for Reviewers	The promotion committee members for each Faculty attended a Faculty-specific training session, led by the PVC Executive Dean and a senior HR representative, to prepare for the promotion process and reviewing applications.	5-7: The workshop provided training and guidance to reviewers, communicated the tools and resources available to staff to support them with the assessment of promotional applications, and communicated the commitment of SU to research assessment reform	n/a	02/25	n/a

Please make sure that funding acknowledgement is added to all your publications.

Please link your publications/outputs in the following Zenodo community [“CoARA Boost Cascade Funding Beneficiaries”](#). For support, please refer to the guidelines in Annex 1.

Please use the following title format to name your documents: “CoARA Boost CF1 - [*Acronym of the project/3 first words of your project title*] - [*Document title*]”

Example (fictive): CoARA Boost CF1 - COSMOS - Booklet for Strategic Meeting”

2.2.2. Narrative assessment of progress

Period 1 - reporting deadline: June 25th, 2025

The narrative assessment of progress should detail current progress, including successes and hurdles encountered during implementation of the workplan.

If your project is organised in WPs, please mention the title and give a summary of work/tasks conducted in each.

Please detail your progress’ narrative assessment in the box below.

The project has run alongside the Swansea University’s existing timetable for academic promotions, with the evaluation feeding into an annual process review, and informing improvements for the following promotion cycle. A Research Analyst has been employed to carry out all tasks detailed in the work plan submitted, with the support of the PI, Research Culture Manager, and other key CoARA stakeholders across the university.

Tasks 1-3 are covered within the MO-M6 period within the Work Plan submitted:

Task 1: Invitations to academic staff to apply for promotion (September 2024- December 2024), planned activity will include support for staff applying for promotions in the guise of training, webinars, workshops and mentoring.

Progress on Task 1: The application window for academic staff to apply for promotion at Swansea University was extended by three months to March 31st, 2025, by Human Resources (HR). Consequently Task 1 was not completed until this date of March 2025.

The promotion process within Swansea is a HR driven process, beyond the scope of this project: “Evaluating the Impact of Reformed Research Assessment and the use of Narrative CVs in Academic Career Promotion at Swansea University”. The project was timely coordinated to align with the academic promotion process, meaning the extension of the application window has delayed some aspects of the project by three months. The university potential cohort of staff that could apply for promotion during the application window of September 2024- March 2025 was 422: 160 Lecturers, 141 Senior Lecturers

and 121 Associate Professors. The actual number of staff that applied was 186 or 44% of the potential pool (see Table 1).

Table 1: Potential and Actual Cohorts of staff on Research-led Academic Career Pathways in the 2024/2025 Swansea University promotion process

University - Pool (ERR & R)		University - Applied (ERR & R)		
Lecturers	160	Applied for SL	77	48%
Senior Lecturers	141	Applied for AP	66	47%
Associate Professors	121	Applied for Prof	43	36%
Total	422	Total	186	44%

Progress has been made with the planned activities within Task 1:

Mentoring support (beyond line manager support at Professional Development Review) was provided to promotion applicants in the form of an online list (pool) of diverse potential mentors from across the university, that candidates could contact directly for support (which included a pool of 72 mentors for staff applying for Senior Lecturer, 66 mentors for Associate Professor, and 61 mentors for Professor applicants). We aim to seek feedback from mentors in the M7-M12 period.

*Training and resources for applicants and reviewers were available on the intranet including a promotions “Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs)” page, a “STEP by STEP Guide” detailing the process, and “ACADEMIC PROMOTION PROCESS FLOWCHART” and “Swansea University - Procedure for Promotion” documents for each grade. [Academic Career Pathway \(ACP\) criteria](#) for the four pathways (Education pathway, Research and Education pathway (Research strand), Research and Education pathway (Education strand), and Research pathway) for each grade and ACP Policy were available to all staff to view online and are openly available on the Swansea University webpages. ACP criteria are intended to provide an indication of the outcomes expected at each grade of the academic scale, to assist members of staff considering an application for promotion. The criteria were used to inform the decisions of promotions committees. Given the range of academic activity the criteria cannot be definitive but will act as a guide to reviewers and applicants. Academic staff were also invited to an informational **Webinar and Q&A** with the PVC of Research & Innovation and the PVC of Education, to assist staff in applying for academic promotion. In addition, the promotion committee members for each Faculty attended a Faculty-specific **training session**, led by the PVC Executive Dean and a senior HR representative, to prepare for the promotion process and reviewing applications.*

We will be seeking feedback on the support and resources available to applicants and reviewers within the framework evaluation surveys which will feed into recommendations and evaluation report that will be produced during the M7-M12 project period.

Task 2: Undertake Process evaluation of resources and support provided to applicants, panels and reviewers (December 2024 - June 2025). The markers of success will be having a Research analyst in post by December 2024, self-Evaluation framework adapted for use by December/January when the anonymised data capture will begin from both applicants and reviewers.

***Progress on Task 2:** The extension of the application window for academic promotion of staff at Swansea University to 31st March 2025, has meant a shift in the timeframe of Task 2 to December 2024 - September 2025. We have successfully recruited a Research Analyst to post, who has co-created the Swansea evaluation framework with guidance from HR and other key stakeholders. As part of the university's commitment to Open Research (OR), we have asked for feedback from the cohort on the use of OR practice as evidence of research capacity within applications, and around the openness and transparency of the promotion process at Swansea University, to help make improvements in support of Responsible Research Assessment.*

The framework has been uploaded to Microsoft forms and translated into Welsh (Cymraeg) in accordance with [Welsh Language Act](#). We have obtained ethics to enable sharing of anonymised data outputs generated from the evaluation survey's from reviewers and applicants. We have are currently awaiting ethical approval for an amendment to the ethics application number 1 2025 13385 12773, to gain approval for consent from participants to perform quantitative and qualitative data analysis on the Research Capacity element/ Narrative style CV only of their promotion application with searches for key words such as "Open Research", "REF", "mentoring", "leadership", and any terms relating to equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI). Data analysis methods will include a mixed-methods approach. Regarding survey results, textual data will be analysed using discourse analysis to investigate recurring themes, identify linguistic patterns, and quantify overarching concepts encoded within language.

For participants who consent to further study, analysis will be conducted on the Research Capacity/ narrative style CV element of their applications. The data will first be analysed qualitatively using corpus analysis, followed by qualitative analysis using a Critical Discourse lens.

The survey will be sent out upon decision from Ethical Review. Results will be analysed within the second period of the project (M7-M12). The HR Equalities team will provide an

anonymised Equality Impact Assessment of the cohort in the second period of the project (M7-M12).

The project has identified gatekeepers to information and data that would enrich the project, which have meant some barriers to accessing data. HR committed to maintaining confidentiality in the promotion process at Swansea University. All documentation relating to the promotions process is treated in the strictest confidence by all parties involved. To maintain anonymity of the promotion cohort, all communication regarding the project has been led by HR. The project has received applicant contact details only with their prior consent. Initial feedback received from applicants about the pilot study consisted of many positive responses but also several queries around being identifiable in research project outputs because of the level of detail and specificity in their application. In response to this feedback, we have created a fact sheet with FAQs for staff to access. We have asked for feedback from the cohort around openness and transparency of the promotion process to help make improvements in support of Responsible Research Assessment.

Task 3: Narrative CV impact assessment #1: (January - July 2025) Data analysis evaluating how the narrative CV is being used by reviewers and panels, and how this is changing the way research is assessed and recognised.

Progress on Task 3: *As described above, there have been delays in sending out the evaluation framework to applicants and reviewers due to the extension of the academic promotions application window by a further 3 months. The timeframe for task 3 has shifted to April - October 2025. The survey will be sent out upon decision from Ethical Review. Results will be analysed within the M7-M12 period of the project.*

2.3. Dissemination activities

Include in this section where your project information was disseminated or if outputs achieve impact.

Please add as many rows as required.

Name		
Please specify the type of activity (e.g. webinar, presentations' slides, ...)	Link	Target audience

CoARA action plan	Swansea University Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment - Action plan	CoARA community
Webinar and Q&A with Pro Vice Chancellor of Research & Innovation	n/a	Academic staff eligible for promotion at Swansea University (SU)
Promotion training with PVC Executive Deans for each of the 3 faculty promotion committees	n/a	Reviewers
Ethics application for consent to share anonymised data outputs from the research	Ethics application number: <i>1 2025 13385 12773</i>	Wider community, CoARA National Chapter, CoARA Cascade community, Higher Education Institutions interested in ARRA
CoARA Cascade SU information sheet and Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs)	n/a (plan to create a Doi and Zenado for the info sheet)	Academic staff (& other staff), to be shared with the wider community interested in ARRA
Reviewer and Applicant evaluation surveys (based on the shared evaluation framework developed by Alternative Users Group and Joint Framework Group)	n/a (plan to share the adapted evaluation surveys later in the project)	Academics and reviewers at SU, once shared the wider community interested in ARRA

2.4. Next steps

The “next steps” section should detail future actions, including activities and decisions, to be taken and/or implemented to achieve the project.

Please describe the **future action and activities planned for the M7 - M12 period** in the box below.

Due to the 3-month extension of the promotion application window at Swansea University, parts of **Tasks 2 and 3** will extend into the M&-M12 period (as described in detail above). During the progression of the project, based on review of the resources available to staff to support the promotion process, the promotion mentorship pool will be contacted to ask for feedback on the promotion process and support provided. This further evaluation was not detailed in the original application but has evolved during progress of the project.

The following tasks from the grant application timeline are planned for M7-M12:

Task 4: Making the evaluation transparent, creating and sharing anonymised evidence gathered from using a Framework co-created between academics and funders of research (September-October 2025). A report will be drafted and shared on webpages, and with community via networks, with recommended changes reviewed and implemented ahead of the promotions window re-opening. The outcomes will be used to draft a paper for publication.

Task 5: Narrative CV impact assessment #2: (September-December 2025) Understand how the narrative CV is being completed and assessed, to support continuous improvement and to make improvements in support of Responsible Assessment

Task 6: To facilitate sharing best practice and lessons learned across the wider research findings and outcomes shared with community to include the UK National CoARA Chapter, the CoARA working group on academic assessment reform, the UKRI R4RI Alternative Uses Group and the Wales Innovation Network. (September- November 2025)

Task 7: Establish an annual evaluation framework (September- November 2025) with outcomes captured in an annual report, drafted to evaluate the tools, processes and practices of research assessment reform, providing important data over time for further improvement.

2.5. Budget monitoring

Please note that this Monitoring Report template covers the technical aspect of the progress reporting and that the Excel table “Project Budget template” covers the financial part. Please fill in the Excel table according to your type of project:

- Annex 4 - for mono-beneficiary (i.e., Institutional Pilot Calls and Institutional Change Calls):

<https://coara.eu/app/uploads/2025/02/Projects-budget-template-unique-partner-1.xlsx>

OR

- Annex 5 - for partnering projects (i.e., Teaming Calls - each partner must complete one sheet in the document):

<https://coara.eu/app/uploads/2025/02/Projects-budget-template-partnering-projects-1.xlsx>

Both documents are mandatory and expected to be submitted to complete the reporting milestones in M06 and M12.

Annex 1 - Guidelines for CoARA signatories on uploading outputs files to the CoARA community on Zenodo

Step 1: Accessing Zenodo

Go to the Zenodo website: <https://zenodo.org/>

Sign in to your Zenodo account using your credentials. If you do not have an account, you can create one by following the registration process.

Step 2: Uploading Your Outputs/Publications

From your Zenodo dashboard, click on the "Upload" button. Choose "Publication" from the content types.

1. **Select the output/publication file** from your computer that you wish to upload. Ensure that your file is in an appropriate format (e.g., PDF, Word document).
2. **Fill in the required metadata**, including title, authors, description, and keywords. Please ensure that you mention "CoARA" in the keywords for easy identification.
3. **For the "DOI,"** you can choose to either:
 - Leave it blank if you don't have a specific DOI in mind and click "Reserve DOI" if you would like one to be auto-generated for this submission.
 - If you have a DOI that you would like to associate with this submission, enter it in the provided field.
4. **Under "Communities,"** select **"CoARA Boost Cascade Funding beneficiaries"** to associate your upload with our community.
5. **Review the licensing options** and select the one that aligns with your preferences for sharing and reuse.
6. **Click Save and Publish** to submit your file.

Step 3: Notify CoARA Secretariat

Please send an email to secretariat@coara.eu once you have uploaded your output/publication. Include the title and DOI of your upload for easy reference.

Note: If you have multiple versions of the output/publication, we kindly ask you to create a new version on Zenodo rather than uploading separate files.